

The Role of Self-Control Moderation in the Influence of E-Money Payment on the Consumptive Behavior of Female Employees in Denpasar City

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ABSTRACT: The city of Denpasar, as the center of economic and cultural activities in Bali, has experienced an increase in the use of digital technology, including e-money, in daily transactions. E-money offers convenience and speed in payments, which can increase the frequency and number of consumptive transactions. Female employees, like other demographic groups, are vulnerable to consumptive behavior. Factors such as advertising, social pressure, and a desire to show social status can drive them to make impulsive or unplanned purchases. This study aims to analyze the variables that affect the consumptive behavior of female employees in the city of Denpasar. The character of female employees who are impulsive in shopping and poor financial planning must be given an immediate solution. This study analyzes the role of self-control moderation on the influence of e-money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar. Descriptive measurements and analysis were carried out to obtain an image or portrait of the respondent. The results of the descriptive measurement are then used as a basis for conducting statistical analysis. Data was collected through a questionnaire instrument (Likert Scale) that has been tested for validity and reliability. Meanwhile, the sample was determined as many as 70 people by incidental sampling technique. Furthermore, the collected data was analyzed using the Partial Least Square analysis technique. The results showed that E-money payment had a positive and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar, Self-control had a negative and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar, Self-control was able to moderate the influence of E-money payment significantly on consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar This can be reflected that self-control can weaken the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar.

KEYWORDS: E-money, Lifestyle, Self Control, consumptive behavior, female employees

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of science and technology has had a considerable impact and has changed the standard of living and consumption patterns in the community. (Khairi and Gunawan, 2019). People want convenience in various aspects of life to meet their daily needs, including in terms of transactions (Puspitasari and Indrarini, 2021). Payment patterns and instruments in economic transactions continue to change (Lintangsari et al., 2018). Initially, the payment system in Indonesia was only limited to direct cash payments (S. Ulayya and E. Mujiasih, 2020). However, along with the development of financial technology (fintech), new innovations have emerged in the implementation of electronic payment transactions (Sari et al., 2020). One of the non-cash payment instruments that is currently developing in Indonesia is electronic money commonly called e-money (S. Priambodo and B. Prabawani, 2016).

Since its introduction in 2008, the use of electronic money in Indonesia has continued to grow. Currently, however, its use is not as much as cash transactions (Fitriana and Wingdes, 2017). Electronic money can be used as a means of payment at certain merchants that collaborate with electronic money issuers. E-money is essentially cash that is converted into electronic data stored on a storage medium on a card in the form of a chip or server. The function of e-money is not much different from the function of cash. The use of electronic money (e-money) is carried out by transferring funds electronically to merchants by directly reducing the value of electronic money on media managed by electronic money holders (Usman, 2017). The use of e-money, which is increasing every year, is stated to have an influence on consumptive behavior. This is evidenced by research conducted by Luh Gede Kusuma Dewi (2017), Hermin Nainggolan (2022), Diah Indiani (2022), Priscilla Irene Sudiro (2022) and Dwi Rorin Mauludin Insana (2020) stating that the use of e-money has a significant direct effect on consumptive behavior. However, behind this convenience, there is an increased risk of consumptive behavior. Many people are tempted to make impulse purchases or spend more than they planned, especially since cashless transactions tend to feel less physically compared to using cash.

According to the Financial Services Authority (OJK), Indonesian people are increasingly consumptive and have begun to abandon the habit of saving. The consumptive behavior of the Indonesian people is classified as excessive when compared to countries in Southeast Asia. The problem of people's low interest in saving is based on the behavior of people who are still reluctant

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to save, and use the money they already have for consumptive things (Perdana, 2016). Consumptive behavior is behavior that consumes excessively and unplanned goods or services that are not needed (Fikri, 2021). Factors that cause consumptive behavior are cashless transactions, the convenience of online shopping applications, lifestyle, peers, and financial literacy.

High consumptive behavior can have a detrimental impact. This is reinforced by research conducted by Nina and Koentjoro (in Astuti, 2013) that excessive consumptive behavior causes prolonged financial problems. Prelec and Loewenstein (in Runnemark, Hedman, & Xiao, 2015) propose the concept of "the pain of paying", i.e., individuals will spend more money with the e-money system than with cash. Individuals will feel more about losing money when sorting cash directly. The less transparent a payment is (the fewer individuals feel the outflow of money), the less likely it is for individuals to spend money. This is supported by research conducted by Citibank India, stating that the use of non-cash transactions or e-money will increase spending by an average of 230 cents more compared to the use of cash (Johnson, 2011). Individuals' desire to make purchases with e-money increases by 22-54% compared to cash. This causes many individuals to prefer to continue using cash to control their spending. E-money is considered to increase the risk of losing control in spending money and causing impulse buying. (Runnemark et al., 2015).

Table 1.1E-Money User Value

Year	Electronic Money Transaction Value (Rupiah)	Percentage
2020	504,96	
2021	786,17	5,73%
2022	1.177,807	7,98%

Source: Bank Indonesia

The increase every year shows that Electronic Money is often used and increasingly in demand by the public (Mustajab, 2023). Mujahidin and Astuti (2020), Khairi and Gunawan (2019), and Giswandhani and Hilmi (2020) stated that the use of debit cards or electronic money has a positive and significant influence on consumptive behavior, while Ramadani (2016) 5 stated that in college adolescents, the use of ATM cards or debit cards has a negative impact because it makes students more consumptive.

Consumer shopping behavior in Indonesia also does not only focus on one type of product, but also on other types of products such as clothing, books, electronic goods, hobby needs, cosmetics, and accessories (Techinasia, 2018). One of the factors that determines the tendency of consumptive behavior in e-money users is personality (Dharmmesta & Handoko, 2013). Self-control is the ability to control or control behavior that is included in one of the personality traits that influence a person in making purchases. The initial research conducted by researchers on 30 female employees by distributing an open questionnaire consisting of several questions, and the results showed that most of the subjects liked to buy and consume products to shop online through social media such as Instagram, Shopee, TikTok, Facebook, WhatsApp, Tokopedia, Lazada.

. However, three of the thirty subjects in the study chose not to shop online because the first subject chose to shop to buy from their close friends, while two subjects chose to shop offline at the market and occasionally borrow accounts from their friends because the subjects did not have a personal account. From the results of the above study, it can be concluded that most of the subjects in the study tend to consume a product purchased online through their social media.

The ease of buying and selling transactions today makes female employees vulnerable by behaving consumptively. Employees need to control themselves with a growing consumptive culture. According to Chita et al. (2015) Self-control describes individual decisions through cognitive considerations to unite behaviors that have been arranged to improve certain outcomes and goals as desired. A person who has low self-control often has difficulty determining the consequences of their actions. A person with high self-control pays great attention to the right ways to behave in varied situations. This statement is supported by the research of Anggreini and Mariyanti (2014) showing that there is a significant negative relationship between self-control and consumptive behavior in Esa Unggul University students. Consumptive behavior occurs due to excessive consumption intentions. This is reinforced by the theory of planned behavior which explains the relationship between beliefs and behavior. This theory also states that an individual's behavioral intention is formed from an attitude, subjective norms and behavioral control. Women who are easily deceived by excessive shopping cravings can develop consumptive behaviors that will ultimately keep them away from achieving healthy finances as expected. Based on the phenomenon described above, the researcher is interested in conducting a study entitled "The Role of Self-Control Moderation on the Influence of E-Money Payment on the Consumptive Behavior of Female Employees in the City of Denpasar

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LITERATUR REVIEW

Financial Literacy

E-MONEY

According to Bayu (2014:3) said that in general, electronic money or in English electronic money is a means of payment that replaces conventional money, can be used and distributed as a medium of exchange stored in digital format on a computer or micro chip in a card. In the provisions of Bank Indonesia Regulation No. 11/12/PBI/2009 concerning Electronic Money in the provisions of Article 1 Paragraph 3, "Electronic Money is a means of payment issued on the basis of the value of money deposited in advance by the holder to the issuer" The value of money is stored electronically in a server media or chip used as a means of payment to merchants who are not the issuers of the electronic money. The value of electronic money deposited by the holder and managed by the issuer is not a deposit as referred to in the law regulating banking

Self-Control

According to Ghufroon and Risnawita (2014), self-control is an individual's ability to be sensitive to reading their own situation and environment. Self-control in terms of financial management is an activity that encourages a person to make savings by reducing impulse purchases (Otto, et al 2004). This refers to the reason that a person's success or not is also influenced by self-control (Tangney, et al 2004). Self-control usually involves trying to avoid short-term preferences in order to achieve long-term preferences (Karlsson, 1998). Thus, self-control in financial management is a strategy used by individuals to prevent waste in financial allocation.

Consumptive Behavior

According to Haryani and Herwanto (2015:7) stated that consumptive behavior is a form of behavior to buy a product without rational consideration or not based on needs, such as buying goods because of the gifts offered, or buying goods because many people use the goods. Meanwhile, according to Dikria and Mintarti (2016), consumptive behavior is defined as the tendency to buy or consume an item that is actually needed excessively, and is not based on rational considerations, so that the desire factor is more important than the need. According to Fattah, et al. (2018:12) consumptive behavior is the behavior of buying goods without strong consideration and prioritizing desires over needs. Gumulya and Widiastuti (2012) define consumptive behavior as the act of buying goods with emotional considerations that are more dominated by desires beyond needs and only to fulfill desires.

Research Hypothesis

- H.1 E-money payment have a positive and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in the city of Denpasar.
- H.2 Self Control have a negative and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in the city of Denpasar.
- H.3 Self Control Moderating Influence E-money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in the city of Denpasar

RESEARCH METHODS

This study was conducted by testing and analyzing the Role of Self-Control Moderation on the Effect of E-Money Payment on the Consumptive Behavior of Female Employees in Denpasar City. This research is quantitative, because it uses numerical data or numbers as the research data that is analyzed to reach conclusions. The nature of this study is explanatory research, which aims to explain the causal relationship between the variables observed in this study in this study, the study population is female employees in Denpasar. The sample size for SEM with the maximum likelihood estimation model is 100 – 200 samples (Ghozali, 2004), or as many as five times the number of indicators (5 x 14 indicators = 70 samples). The sampling process or sampling technique is carried out by incidental sampling according to the criteria of female employees in Denpasar.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

Convergent Validity

Table 1 Outer Loading Value of Estimated Results before Execution

	E-Money Payment	Moderation	Consumptive - Behaviur	Self-Control
E-Money Payment * Self-Control		1,037		
M1				0,866
M2				0,860
M3				0,648
X12	0,949			
X13	0,653			

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Y1			0,863	
Y2			0,865	
Y3			0,836	
Y4			0,883	
Y5			0,840	
Y6			0,816	
Y7			0,853	
X11	0,790			

Source: Data processed, 2024

Figure 1 before execution

Based on the results of data analysis, there are several values that have not met the outer model values consisting of convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability (the RhoA value has a negative value). So there are several indicators that are removed from the model. The indicator includes X1.3 of the e-,money payment variable. Indicators Y1 and Y4 of the consumptive behavior variable

Table 2 Outer Loading Value of Estimated Results after Execution

	E-Money Payment	Moderation	Consumtive -Behavior	Self-Control
E-Money Payment * Self-Control		1,022		
M1				0,858
M2				0,870
M3				0,626
X12	0,927			
Y2			0,864	
Y3			0,824	
Y5			0,877	
Y6			0,805	
Y7			0,876	
X11	0,866			

Source : Data processed, 2024

. All indicators meet convergent validity

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Figure 2 after execution

Validity of Discrimination

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	E-Money Payment	Moderation	Saving-Behaviour	Self-Control
E-Money Payment	0,897			
Moderation	-0,089	1,000		
Consumptive -Behavior	-0,034	0,093	0,850	
Self-Control	-0,031	-0,182	-0,172	0,793

The AVE value of all constructs > 0.50 and the \sqrt{AVE} value (which is blocked in yellow) of each construct ranges from 0.793 to 1.000 which is greater than the correlation value which is between -0.031 to 0.093 so that it meets the valid criteria based on the discriminant validity criterion

Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

A measurement can be said to be reliable, if the composite reliability and cronbach alpha have values greater than 0.60 - 0.70. Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha are a measure of reliability between indicator blocks in the research model.

Table 3 Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alph Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
E-Money Payment	0,762	0,806	0,892	0,805
Moderation	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
Consumptive - Behavior	0,903	0,903	0,928	0,722
Self-Control	0,761	0,706	0,832	0,628

Source: data processed,2024

The composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha values of each construct have shown a value greater than 0.60 so that they meet the reliability criteria based on the composite reliability criteria.

Structural Model/Inner Model Evaluation

Structural Model Evaluation (Structural Model/Inner Model) is a measurement to evaluate the accuracy of the model in the overall study, which is formed through several variables along with their indicators.

1) Evaluation of Structural Models Through R-Square (R2)

R Square Test

Inner Model Test Results

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Table 4 R SQUARE

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Consumtive -Behaviur	0,035	-0,009

Source : Data processed, 2024

The R2 value of saving behavior is 0.035 based on the Chin criterion (Ghozali, 2021), so the model is included in the weak model criterion, where e-money payment, the interaction of e-money payment with self-control has a weak influence on consumptive behavior of 0.035

2. Test F Square

Table 5 F Square Test Results

	Saving-Behaviur
E-Money Payment	0,001
E-money*self control	0,004
Consumtive -Behaviur	
Self-Control	0,026

Source: Data processed, 2024

Based on the results of the analysis, e-money payment has a small influence on consumptive behavior of 0.001. Self-control had a small effect on consumptive behavior of 0.026. The interaction of e-money with self-control had a small effect on consumptive behavior of 0.004.

Path Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The expected path of analysis and testing of the hypothesis is that Ho is rejected or the sig value < 0.05 (or the statistical t-value > 1.96 with a level of significance 0.05).

Table 6 Path Analysis and Statistical Testing

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
E-Money Payment -> consumptive behaviour	0,033	2,760	0,035	e money has a positive and significant effect on consumptive behavior
E-money*self control-> consumptive behaviour	-0,059	2,312	0,020	The interaction of e money with self-control has a significant negative effect on consumptive behavior
Self-Control -> consumptive behaviour	-0,162	3,154	0,025	Self-control has a negative and significant effect on consumptive behavior

Source : Data processed, 2024

Figure C 3. Structural Model of Estimation Results

Source: Data processed, 2024

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data processing shown in Table 6, the discussion of the research results

1) The effect of e-money on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar

Providing e-money information has a positive and significant effect on consumptive behavior, where the path coefficient shown by e-money has a positive influence of 0.033 with t-statistics $2.760 > out of 1.96$. The results of this test show that Hypothesis 1 (H_1) is accepted, with a significance of 0.035 less than 0.005. This means that the use of e-money has a positive and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar. The results of this study are in line with previous research by Shiega et al., (2024), e money has a positive and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of generation Z Research. The results of research by Widiantari et al. (2023) stated that there is a positive and significant influence of e money on the financial behavior of generation Z in the city of Denpasar cashless society

2) The effect of self-control on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar

Providing information that control cells showed a negative and significant influence on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar, where the pathway coefficient was -0.162 with a t-statistic of $3.154 > from 1.96$. Self-control had a negative influence of -0.162 on saving behavior, with a significant 0.025 greater than 0.005 . The results of this test show that Hypothesis 2 (H_2) is accepted, which means that self-control has a negative and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees. This result is in line with research conducted by Lim, et al (2011) that a person who has good self-control can behave frugally. This is due to internal opposition to needs and desires. Research Nofsinger, J. R. (2018); Tripambudi, A., & Indrawati, L. (2018) stated the effect of self-control on consumptive behavior to reduce waste through desire control.

3) Self-control moderates the influence of E money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar

Providing information that self-control is able to moderate the influence of e-money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar. The interaction of e-money payment with self-control has an influence of -0.059 on consumptive behavior, with a significance of

0.020 is less than 0.005 . This means that the interaction of e-money payment with self-control has a negative and significant effect on consumptive behavior. The results of this test show that Hypothesis 3 (H_3) is accepted This means that self-control moderates the influence of e money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar. Previous research has indicated that a consumptive lifestyle can weaken the effect of self-control on consumptive behavior. Hidayah, A. F. (2019) stated, individuals with a more materialistic or consumptive lifestyle tend to have a greater chance of impulsive behavior, even though they have a high level of self-control)

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The limitations of this study are: The nature of this research is cross-sectoral, considering that this research is only conducted at one time and is not continuous. This study does not try to compare the perception of the research object in a continuous period of time so that it can reveal more phenomena in the research. So, this study suggests investigating other antecedents of consumptive behavior in a knowledge-intensive context in future research This study sampled female employees in Denpasar. This study does not take a broader object so that the results of this study are a generalization of the respondents' answers used as a sample

CONCLUSION

- 1 E-money payment has a positive and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar.
- 2 Self-control has a negative and significant effect on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar
- 3 Self-control is able to moderate the influence of significant E-money payment on the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar This can be reflected that self-control can weaken the consumptive behavior of female employees in Denpasar

SUGGESTIONS

1. For female employees, the results of this study are expected to give an idea that the use of e-money payment and self-control is an important determining factor. consumptive behavior of female employees in the city of Denpasar. The role of the government in creating these conditions is very large. The government is expected to participate in increasing self-control and financial literacy related to e-money for the community, especially female employees so that they are able to reduce consumptive behavior
2. For Other Researchers
For other researchers, it is possible to re-examine other variables that affect the consumptive behavior of female employees based on the theory that has been revealed

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